

H2020-SC5-01-2017

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 4.4

Assessment of the added value for the decision-making process for the durum wheat sector

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776467.

DOCUMENT STATUS SHEET

Deliverable Title	Assessing the added value of the pilot service to the user in Durum wheat sector	
Brief Description	This deliverable aims to assess the added value of the new functionality of Granoduro.net in Durum wheat sector through an online survey.	
WP number		WP5
Lead Beneficiary	<i>logo</i>	
Contributors	<i>Mehri Khosravi, Marta Bruno Soares</i>	
Creation Date	30/03/2018	
Version Number		
Version Date		
Deliverable Due Date	31/04/2021	
Actual Delivery Date	31/04/2021	
Nature of the Deliverable		<i>R - Report P - Prototype D - Demonstrator O - Other</i>
Dissemination Level/ Audience		<i>PU - Public PP - Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission services RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services</i>

REVISION HISTORY LOG

Version	Date	Created / Modified by	Pages	Comments
1.0	30-04-2021	LEEDS UNI	32	Initial Draft
2.0	20-05-2021	LEEDS UNI	31	Revised version

All partners involved in the production/implementation of the deliverable should comment and report (if needed) in the above table. The above table should support the decisions made for the specific deliverable in order to include the agreement of all involved parties for the final version of the document.

Finally, after the peer review process, the deliverable should be modified accordingly to the comments and the reflections to the comments should be reported in the above table.

Disclaimer

The information, documentation, tables and figures in this deliverable are written by the MED-GOLD project consortium under EC gran agreement 776467 and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. OBJECTIVES	6
2. IMPACT	6
3. DEFINITIONS	7
4. ACRONYMS	7
5. REFERENCES	8
6. DETAILED REPORT	9
6.1. Summary on WP4	9
6.2 Methodology to assess the added value of Granoduro.net	11
6.2.1 Conceptual framework	12
6.2.2 Survey structure	13
6.2.3 Survey Dissemination	13
6.3 Survey Results	14
7. Conclusion	23
8. Annex: Survey	24

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1-1 project objectives	6
Table 2-1: Expected impacts of the deliverable	6
Table 3-1 Definitions	7
Table 4-1 Acronyms	7
Table 5-1 Reference Documents	8 7
Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of the indicators that identified during users assessment in wheat sector	10
Figure 6.2. Methodology to assess the usability of the new functionality of Granoduro.net	11
Figure 6.3 Adapted conceptual framework to assess the usability of the Med-Gold pilot services	13
Figure 6.4 Type of participants' role (N=12)	14
Figure 6.5 Types of climate information needs according to types of activities	15
Figure 6.6 Type of climatic variables needed according to types of activities	16
Figure 6.7 Type of decisions which can be support by the tool	17
Figure 6.8 Potential benefits of using the tool in decision-makings	18
Figure 6.9 Participants responses to the tool accessibility	18 19
Figure 6.10 Participants responses to the tool's understandability	19
Figure 6.11 Participants responses to the tool' climate variables	19 20
Figure 6.12 Participants responses to the tool' providing the information at the right time	20
Figure 6.13 Participants responses to the tool' providing the information at the right lead time	20 24
Figure 6.14 Participants responses to the tool's data reliability	21
Figure 6.15 External factors in the sector	22

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Work Package4 (WP4) aims to co-develop a climate service(s) in Durum wheat sector and started with assessing the climate information needs/decisions in wheat sector in Task 4.1. Climate services to provide WP4' climate information needs were developed in a close interaction between the end-users including BARILLA and climate scientists in task 4.2 and were then tested in the following task. Task 4.4 aims to assess the added value of the developed tools to the Durum wheat sector. This deliverable presents the assessment which was done through an online survey. The assessment started with developing a conceptual framework which has been explained in Section 6.2.1. The conceptual framework was then translated into the survey questions as presented in annex 1. The final version of Granoduro.net developed by MED-GOLD was presented to the users (farmers and elevators) through an online workshop held by Barilla in Feb 2021 then the online survey link was sent to the users to assess the added value of the tool to their activities.

The assessment reveals that the new functionality of Granoduro.net is salient enough for the users as they believe the tool is easy to access, and they have the variables, indicators and the lead time they need to make decision in their roles. However, regarding the data understandability, five users out of eight agreed that the data is easy to understand and some users have mentioned that they need training to be able to use and apply the information provided in the tool in their decision-making. Reliability of the climate information is the factor that users are not completely sure about it. The details of the result have been explained in section 6.3.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

Table 1-1 project objectives

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	X
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

2. IMPACT

This deliverable aims to assess the added value of the new functionality of Granoduro.net in Durum wheat sector. The provision of climate services may not necessarily lead to the desired outcome of increased agricultural productivity due to a variety of reasons and obstacles (Vogel et al., 2017). This assessment could help us to identify such obstacles and ensure sufficient engagement with end users in the development of climate services within the sector. The added value assessment of the climate service in the sector was done through an online survey and this deliverable provides the result of the assessment.

Table 2-1: Expected impacts of the deliverable

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimised risk	X
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 3-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Climate service	Climate Services involve the (co-)production, transfer, and use of tailored climate information products to improve decision-making at different scales (Vaughan and Dessai, 2014).
Value	The word 'value' has been defined as the range of benefits (economic and/or non-economic) that can be gained from using climate information in decision-making (Bruno Soares et al., 2018).

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 4-1 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CNR	National Research Council
DSS	Decision Support System
MED-GOLD	Referring to the project entitled "Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems"
RD	Reference documents
WP	Work Package

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document.

Table 5-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	First Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	D 4.6		2020
[RD.2]	Second Feedback report from users on durum wheat pilot service development	D 4.7		2020
[RD.3]	Bruno Soares M, Alexander M, Dessai S .2018. Sectoral use of climate information in Europe: a synoptic overview. <i>Climate Service</i> 9:5–20.			2018
[RD.4]	Lemos MC .2008.What influences innovation adoption by water managers? <i>Climate information use in Brazil and the United States. JAWRA J Am Water Resour Assoc</i> 44(6):1388–1396.			2008
[RD.5]	Lemos, M. C., K. S. Wolske, L. V. Rasmussen, J. C. Arnott, M. Kalcic, and C. J. Kirchoff, 2019: The Closer, the Better? Untangling Scientist–Practitioner Engagement, Interaction, and Knowledge Use. <i>Weather. Climate Society.</i> , 11, 535–548, https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-18-0075.1 .			2018
[RD.6]	McNie EC .2007. Reconciling the supply of scientific information with user demands: an analysis of the problem and review of the literature. <i>Environment Science Policy</i> 10(1):17–38. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2006.10.004 .			2007
[RD.7]	Robinson J, Tansey J .2006.Co-production, emergent properties and strong interactive social research: the Georgia Basin Futures Project. <i>Sci Public Policy</i> , 33(2):151–160.			2006
[RD.8]	Tall, A. Coulibaly, J.Y. Diop, M. 2018. Do climate services make a difference? A review of evaluation methodologies and practices to assess the value of climate information services for farmers: Implications for Africa. <i>Climate Services</i> 11: 1–12. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cliser.2018.06.001 .			2018
[RD.9]	Tall, A., and Njinga, J. 2013. Developing a methodology to evaluate climate services for farmers in Africa and South Asia workshop report. Copenhagen, Denmark: CGIAR Program on Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security. Retrieved from www.ccafs.cgiar.org .			2013
[RD.10]	VanderMolen, K. Meadow, A.M. Horangic, A. Wall, T.U. 2020. Typologizing Stakeholder Information Use to Better Understand the Impacts of Collaborative Climate Science. <i>Environmental Management</i> 65:178–189 https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-019-01237-9 .			2020
[RD.11]	Vincent, K., Daly, M., Scannell, C., Leathes, B., 2018. What can climate services learn from theory and practice of co-production? <i>Clim. Serv.</i> 12, 48–58.			2018
[RD.12]	Vincent, K., Conway, D., Dougill, A.J. Pardoe, J. Archer, E., Bhave, A.G., Henriksson, R., Mittal, N., Mkwambisi, D., Rouhaud, E., Nhlème, DT. Re-balancing climate services to inform climate-resilient planning – A conceptual framework and illustrations from sub-Saharan Africa. <i>Climate Risk Management</i> 29 (2020) 100242.			2020
[RD.13]	Vogel, J., Letson, D., Herrick, C. 2017. A framework for climate services evaluation and its application to the Caribbean Agrometeorological Initiative. <i>Climate Services</i> , 65–76.			2017

6. DETAILED REPORT

6.1. Summary on WP4

The Work Package 4 (WP4) aims to co-develop a climate service(s) in the durum wheat sector and has four main tasks which has been summarise as follows:

Task 1: Assessing the needs/decisions of wheat sector

Two workshops were held on 15th and 16th May 2018 at HORTA Ltd premises in Italy to identify the key decisions and climate information needs in the durum wheat sector. Participants of the first workshop were 11 technical experts from Italian political institutions, breeding, academic world and stocks exchange markets while the latter one involved 15 users of Granoduro.net from farmers and elevators.

Task 2 – Developing tools

This task was conducted to co-develop the MED-GOLD services within Durum wheat sector. This task was done in a close interaction between the end-users including BARILLA and climate scientists in 2019. The development and co-designing phase are results of two users' feedback steps (which were reported in RD.1 and RD.2) that were focused on the understanding of recent past climate and the exploitation of the recent development and availability of seasonal forecasts. Granoduro.net, and Delphi are tools that have been discussed in WP4.

- **Granoduro.net:**

Granoduro.net is an interactive web-based Decision Support System (DSS) for high-quality sustainable wheat farming which is presently used by farmers and technicians in the Barilla supply chain. Granoduro.net' users could be farmers, elevators and policymakers and it can be used as a decision support system for a variety of decisions in wheat sector. The current version of the tool uses observed weather data, short-term weather data forecasts (7-days weather) and crop information entered by the user to provide advice on fertilisation, sowing, wheat phenology, weed management, pest management, water balance. The new functionality of the tool which was done with a co-development approach through MED-GOLD project, uses seasonal forecasts and has three main sections:

- Wheat phenological development;
- Indexes for the risk of wheat diseases;
- Climate indices, developed in the CLISAGRI package: Clisagri is a climate modelling tool that translates the perceived extreme weather and climate conditions into a set of quantitative agro-climate indicators. These 16 indicators support different type of decisions such as fertilization, sowing, and irrigation during crop growth (Figure 6.1).

Figure 6.1: Schematic representation of the indicators that identified during users' assessment in wheat sector.

Delphi

The Delphi is a crop model calibrated and maintained by the National Research Council (CNR). Delphi is used operationally by the CNR in order to provide the forecast of durum wheat yield and quality in Italy to Barilla. The standard Delphi System is driven by the three reference weather scenarios based on historical observations (dry, average, wet scenario) to simulate plant growth from the 1st of September till the harvest date. This version input weather data at daily time scale such as the air temperature (maximum, minimum and average), global shortwave radiation, total precipitation, wind speed (average) and relative humidity (average). Input data for the main physiological parameters of the durum wheat cultivars, sowing date and number of seeds/m², the soil hydrological profile, soil total nitrogen content profile, agronomic data on quality and quantity of nitrogen and roots growth data are also required (RD.1). In MED-GOLD, Delphi has been modified in order to be driven by seasonal forecast data provided by Copernicus Climate Data Store released in October 2017 and consisting of 51-members simulations lasting for 6 months (see RD.2).

Task 3 – Testing the tools

The first users' feedback was collected via a workshop with users in Barilla' premises. The climate indices computed on seasonal forecasts were presented to finalise the list of indicators. Participants were also asked to provide answers to questionnaires that were collected after the workshops (RD. 1). A further feedback is provided by Barilla on the DELPHI yield and biomass seasonal forecasts, following the same questionnaire.

Task 4 – Assessing the value of the new functionality of Granoduro.net

At this stage, the added value of the final version of Granoduro.net is assessed. The assessment could help us to ensure sufficient engagement with end users in the co-development of the climate service. The method of the assessment has been explained in section 6.3 followed by the result in section 6.4. We have not considered Delphi in this assessment as Delphi is only used to support wheat purchase and its users are limited to only four Barilla’s technicians.

6.2 Methodology to assess the added value of Granoduro.net

As figure 6.2 shows the assessment starts with a broad literature review which has been used to develop a conceptual framework underpinning the assessment. The theoretical foundation which underpins the conceptual framework is explained in Section 6.2.1. Then, the framework is translated into questions to shape the online survey in the wheat sector. Survey structure, and its dissemination have been explained in sections 6.2.2 and 6.2.3.

Figure 6.2. Methodology to assess the usability of the new functionality of Granoduro.net

6.2.1 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Although some studies consider accessibility, understandability to define useful climate services (Tall and Njinga, 2013; Tall et al., 2018), this itself has often not translated into use of climate information in decision-making (Lemos et al., 2012; Vincent et al., 2018). This means data availability is only a requirement of using data in decision-making and usability is beyond availability (Vincent et al., 2020). Cash et al. (2003) have classified all usability factors into three main criteria that make information to be usable in decision-making which are credibility, saliency and legitimacy (Lemos 2008; McNie 2007, 2013; Lemos et al., 2012; Lemos et al., 2018; VanderMolen et al, 2020).

Saliency refers to factors such as timeliness of the climate information, spatial scale, appropriate selection of variables, and understandable presentation format (visualisation). This factor means the information needs to be relevant to a decision maker's problem (Gettelman, Rood, 2016). Credibility refers to the quality of scientific information as judged by the standards of the scientific community. It relates to aspects of accuracy, reliability and quality of the data (VanderMolen et al., 2020). Legitimacy is derived from the process used to produce the information, which must be free from any bias and perceived to be transparent by stakeholders (Cash et al. 2006; Lemos 2008; McNie 2007, 2013). A two-way engagement between users and providers of information, can help building legitimacy and transparency (Robinson and Tansey, 2006; Vincent et al., 2018; Vincent et al., 2020).

However, creating useable information, which is salient, credible and legitimate, does not guarantee *per se* the use of the information in decision-making as other factors need to be in place in order to bridge the "usability gap" (Lemos et al., 2012; Vincent et al., 2018; 2020). Such factors include organizational constraints, lack of human resources, or lack of political factors which can hinder application of usable climate information in the decision-making process and adaptation planning (Dilling and Lemos., 2011; Bruno Soares et al. 2018; Lemos et al., 2012). Hence, as figure 6.3 shows use of climate information in decision-making depends on two main group of factors which are (Del. 5.2):

- Internal factors (such as accessibility, saliency, credibility, and legitimacy of data),
- External factors (such as organisational culture, human capacity and so on).

Figure 6.3 Adapted conceptual framework to assess the usability of the MED-GOLD pilot services

6.2.2 SURVEY STRUCTURE

At this stage, the conceptual framework is translated into questions that shape the online survey (Annex 1). The survey is structured in four main sections, including:

Section A: Participants' role,

In first section participants were asked about their primary role in wheat sector and whether they are a user of climate information.

Section B: Climate information needs,

In this section participants were asked what kind of climate information they need to help inform their decisions in their role.

Section C: The usability of Granoduro.net

In this section participants were asked to assess the usability of the tool in wheat sector in terms of saliency, reliability, and legitimacy.

Section D: External factors and recommendations.

In this section participants were asked whether there are any external factors that could limit the use of the tool in their role. We also asked them to provide some recommendations to increase the usability of the tool in their role.

6.2.3 SURVEY DISSEMINATION

The survey draft was sent to WP4 partners to check and comment. It was then translated into Italian and designed by the Survey monkey software. In the meantime, the WP4 held a workshop on 26th Feb 2021 to showcase the final version of Granoduro.net to the users as well as introduce the structure of the survey. Ten users of Granoduro.net participated in the workshop and they were asked to test the tool and fill the

survey. In doing so, the users were given a week to interact with the new version and then the survey link was sent to them early March 2021 and it was closed end of March.

6.3 Survey Results

This section presents the findings, following the responses to the survey (see Section 6.3.2). These findings are organized based on participants’ role, climate information needs, the usability of Granoduro.net, external factors and recommendations.

Section A: Participants’ role:

A total of 14 participants responded to the survey and 12 of them responded to this section. As figure 6.4 shows the respondents were from different roles, six respondents were agronomists, three respondents were farmers and one of them was an elevator.

Figure 6.4 Type of participants’ role (N=12)

Section B: Users’ climate information needs:

Participants were asked whether they are the users of climate information in their current role and all confirmed that they use climate information. They were then asked what climate information they need in their current role. The survey result shows that weather forecast, historical data and seasonal forecast are the most needed data by these users. As figure 6.5 shows, climate projections are not needed for any of the

decisions as it is only used for long-term decisions. Climate predictions could be needed for some decisions such as choice of variety, contract and harvest.

Figure 6.5 Types of climate information needs according to types of activities

According to our sample, precipitation (mean and extreme) and temperature (mean, max, min) are the most needed climate variables for the participants (Figure 6.6). Variables such as wind speed, wind direction and solar radiation are the least needed variables and only needed for decisions such as sowing and fertilisation and crop protections. However, precipitation and temperature are needed for all types of decisions in the sector.

Figure 6.6 Type of climatic variables needed according to types of activities

Section C: The usability of Granoduro.net

To assess the usability of the new functionality of the Granoduro.net, participants were asked to access and test the tool before responding to the survey. Participants were then asked during the survey, if they were able to access and use the tool during the test period. A total of nine participants accessed and used the tool whilst three participants only accessed the tool and two did not use the tool.

The users were further questioned about what kind of decisions they think the new functionality of Granoduro.net could help them in their roles. Three participants responded to this question and stated that the tool could help them with crop protection and fertilisation. Then they were asked whether they have used the tool in the testing period (during the month of March). If so, in what type of decisions the new functionality of Granoduro.net was helpful. As figure 6.7 shows seven participants answered to this question and they confirmed the tool helped them with crop protection and fertilisation.

Figure 6.7 Type of decisions which can be support by the tool

Participants were then asked how the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net could support them in the decisions they selected in previous question. Three participants answered this:

- *"Besides knowing the units of nitrogen, on the base of the forecast I can understand when to distribute them".*
- *"It allows me to know the risk forecasted for the season".*
- *"Information on phenology help me providing the amplitude of the time interval for doing fertilisation. The risk on diseases helps me plan the crop protection interventions months ahead. The climatological indexes help me in the choice of the kind of fertiliser to apply by observing the hydrological balance in the different phase, thus proving a forecast on the amount of water arriving on the ground as rain".*

Potential benefits

The participants were further questioned about the potential benefits they could experience by using the new functionality of Granoduro.net to their activities and they were given some options to select. Ten responded to this question and six were of the opinion that the new functionality could provide them with the anticipated information on the risk of wheat diseases during the growing season. Two participants agreed that the tool could support them in better purchase planning.

Figure 6.8 Potential benefits of using the tool in decision-making

To explore the saliency aspect of the tool, participants were questioned about the tool’s accessibility, understandability, climate variables and right lead time. Regarding to the tools’ accessibility, as Figure 6.9 shows, nine participants responded to this question and six of them agreed or strongly agreed that the tool is easy to access.

Figure 6.9 Participants responses to the tool accessibility

We also asked them whether the information provided by the tool is easy to interpret or understand. Eight participants answered to the question and 5 of them agreed or strongly agreed that the tool is easy to understand (Figure 6.10).

Figure 6.10 Participants responses to the tool's understandability

They were questioned whether the new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the weather and climate variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in the wheat sector. Nine participants responded to this question and eight out of nine agreed that the tool provides the variables or indicators that they need to make decisions in their roles (Figure 6.11).

Figure 6.11 Participants responses to the tool' climate variables

Nine users responded to the question whether the new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the information that users need at the right time to inform different activities and decisions and they strongly agree or agree with it (Figure 6.12).

Figure 6.12 Participants responses to the tool providing the information at the right time

We asked participants whether the new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the information at the right lead time (e.g., from one month to one year ahead of time, etc) to inform different decisions. Eight of them responded and agreed that the tool provides the right lead time that they need in their role (Figure 6.13).

Figure 6.13 Participants responses to the tool providing the information at the right lead time

More importantly, we asked them about the reliability (i.e., the information is trustworthy) of the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net. Ten users answered this question and only six of them

were pretty sure that data seems reliable, and four participants were not sure whether data is reliable or not (Figure 6.14).

Figure 6.14 Participants responses to the tool's data reliability

The participants were also asked whether they have been involved in the development of the new functionality of the Granoduro.net. Nine participants answered this question and the result shows seven of them have been involved in the process.

Section D: External factors and recommendations

In the last question, the participants were asked to rate the factors that could act as a barrier to use the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net from 1 (low) to 5 (high). Result from our sample shows that misconception (lack of trust) of climate information among farmers and Lack of awareness about the benefits of climate forecasts in the decision-making are the main external factors that could hinder the use of seasonal forecasts among participants (Figure 6.15).

Figure 6.15 External factors in the sector

To enhance the usability of the tool the users were asked what changes they would make to the tool. Four participants responded to this question. Two of them said they wouldn't change anything, however, two of them commented that:

"I would improve the presentation of the model's output. I would describe better the indexes and the practical implications in a way we [the users] can get".

" You could implement the tool on fertilisation, suggesting the type of fertiliser to be used (as. Nitric nitrogen, ammoniacal nitrogen...), based on phenology forecasts and the climatic indexes".

We also asked them whether they intend to use the new functionality of Granoduro.net in the future. If so, provide their reasoning. Six users replied that they would use the tool in the future for the following reasons:

- *"I would use to improve the quality and quantity of the product".*
- *" If I find the time to dedicate to learn how to use it".*
- *"I would use it to evaluate the yield forecasts".*
- *" Yes, because it is unique and it will be the start to study and go deep in the predictions on other various themes around the crop of wheat".*
- *"I need training to use the tool, but it is my fault, as I could not participate the on-line workshop".*

7. CONCLUSION

A conceptual framework was adopted to assess the usability of climate services developed in the MED-GOLD project with users who have been directly involved in the co-development process of the tools (Task 2.X). In this deliverable we have applied the framework to assess the usability of the tool developed in WP4 to understand the constraining factors that may lead to the less use of the developed climate services in practice. The assessment reveals that the tool is salient enough for users as they believe the tool is easy to access, and they have the variables, indicators and the lead time they need to make decisions in their roles. However, regarding the **data understandability**, only 5 users (60% of participants) agreed that the data is easy to understand. Moreover, some users have mentioned that they **need training** to be able to use and apply the information provided by the tool in their decision-making. **Reliability** of the climate information is the factor that users are not completely sure about it. Exploring external factors confirms this aspect as the result shows that users believe that the misconception of climate information' inaccuracy can hinder the use of climate information (this means users think the seasonal forecasts is not accurate enough to use). Some users suggested that describing the indices, and better presenting the model output could enhance the tool's usability.

8. ANNEX: SURVEY

Purpose of the survey

The purpose of this survey is to help us assess the new functionality of Granoduro.net, developed within the European project Med-Gold.

Data collection and protection

We will not share the data collected in this survey outside of the Med-Gold project consortium without asking for your permission. By completing this survey, you agree that the data collected will be used in our research and results. If you change your mind about participating within two weeks of filling in the survey, please inform Dr. Mehri Khosravi (f.khosravi@leeds.ac.uk) and your data will be removed from the study.

Completing this survey

This online survey takes approximately 10 minutes to complete. Thank you for taking the time to help us improve the new functionality of Granoduro.net!

Section A: About you

1) What is your primary role?

- Farmer
- Elevator
- Policymaker
- Agronomist
- Wheat breeder
- Other

If other, please specify:

2) Do you use weather and/or climate information in your role?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please go to Q4

If no, please go to Q3

3) What are the main reasons for not using climate information in your role?

- I do not require climate information to perform my activities
- Climate information is difficult to understand for me
- Climate information is not available in a format that is useful for my needs
- Climate information is helpful in my role but there is no obligation to use it

- Climate information is helpful in my role but the organisation lacks in-house expertise to integrate climate information in our activities.
- If other, please specify:

Section B: Users' climate information's needs

4) What type(s) of weather and climate information do you need to help inform your decisions in relation to wheat? (Multiple options may be selected)

	Historical climate information	Weather information hour/day/weeks	Seasonal forecasts (1 to 12 months ahead)	Climate predictions (1 to 9 years ahead)	Climate projections (10 years or more ahead)
Choice of variety					
Sowing date, density					
Soil tillage					
Fertilization					
Weeding					
Crop protection					
Harvest					
Contract and price					
Other (please specify)					

5) What type(s) of weather and climate variables do you need for key decisions in wheat sector? (Multiple options may be selected)

	Temperature			Precipitation		Wind		Soil moisture	Solar radiation	Other (please specify)
	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Extreme	Speed	Direction			
Choice of variety										
Sowing date, density										
Soil tillage										
Fertilization										
Weeding										
Crop protection										

Harvest										
Contract and price										
Other (please specify)										

Section C: The usability of Granoduro.net

6) Have you accessed or used the new functionality of Granoduro.net in the past few weeks to support/inform your decisions?

- Yes, I have accessed and used it to support my activities
- Yes, I have accessed but not used
- No, I have not accessed or used

If a) please go to question 9

If b) or c), please go to questions 7 & 8

7) Could you please describe why you didn't use the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net? (You can choose more than one option)

- The tool is not easy to use.
- The data is not easy to understand or interpret.
- The tool does not provide the variables or indicators I need to make decisions.
- The tool does not provide the information at the right lead time (e.g. from one month to one year ahead of time).
- The data does not seem reliable and trustworthy to use.
- If other, please specify.

8) What kind of decisions do you think the new functionality of Granoduro.net could help you with? (You can choose more than one option)

- Fertilization
- Weeding
- Crop protection
- Contract and price
- If other, please specify:

9) What decisions did the new functionality of Granoduro.net help inform/support your activities? (You can choose more than one option)

- Fertilization
- Weeding
- Crop protection
- Contract and price
- If other, please specify:

10) Please describe how the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net helped you in the decisions you selected in Q9 (e.g. which information/indices helped you to make which decisions)?

11) What kind of potential benefit do you think you could experience by using the new functionality of Granoduro.net on your activities and decision-making.? (Multiple options may be selected).

- Better disease control (e.g. it can provide me the anticipated information on the risk of wheat diseases during the growing season),
- Better purchase planning (e.g. it helps me to predict the amount and type of products I need for the season)
- Improved efficiency (e.g. using indicators such as hydrological balance and excessive wetness could help me in planning crop management).
- Early indication on grain yield and quality (e.g. indicators such as hydrological balance, rain and extreme temperatures could help me in crop management).
- Other, please specify.

12) I could access and use the new functionality of Granoduro.net easily.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

13) The information provided in the new functionality of Granoduro.net is easy to understand.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

14) The new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the weather and climate variables or indicators I need to make decisions in the wheat sector.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

15) The new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the information I need at the right time to inform different activities and decisions.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

16) The new functionality of Granoduro.net provides the information at the right lead time (e.g. from one month to one year ahead of time, etc) to inform different decisions.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

17) The information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net seems reliable (i.e. the information is trustworthy) for me to use in my activities.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Any additional comments?

- 18) Have you been involved in the development of the new functionality of the Granoduro.net?
- Yes
 - No

If the answer was "yes", how were you involved?

Section D: External factors and recommendations

- 19) Do any of the following factors act as a barrier to use the information provided by the new functionality of Granoduro.net, if so please rate them from 1 (low) to 5 (high).

Factors	No barrier	1	2	3	4	5
Insufficient legal requirements to uptake seasonal forecasts						
Insufficient in-house human or technical capacity to use seasonal forecasts or projections in your Organisation,						
Lack of awareness about the benefits of climate forecasts in decision-making,						
Lack of willingness in your organisation to use seasonal forecasts,						
Misconception (lack of trust) of climate information inaccuracy among farmers.						

If there are other factors, please specify.

- 20) What changes would you make to increase the usability of the new functionality of Granoduro.net?
- 21) Do you intend to use the new functionality of Granoduro.net in the future? If so, why?
- 22) Any other comments?

END OF DOCUMENT

